

The Impact of Melaka as a UNESCO World Heritage Tourist Area on the Motivations

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ABSTRACT

Malays will not disappear from the world." The oath of Admiral Hang Tuah in the 15th century seemed to have received his "luck". When UNESCO designated Bandaraya Melaka as a World Heritage City on July 7, 2008, The aim of this research is to determine what factors influence the motivation of tourists visiting the Old City area of Bandaraya Melaka. The research methodology uses quantitative descriptive analysis with a sample size of 37 people. Variable (X1): psychological motivation has no effect on tourist motivation (Y), cultural motivation variable (X2) has no effect on tourist motivation (Y), social motivation variable (X3) has an effect on tourist motivation (Y), and fantasy motivation variable (X4) has an effect on tourist motivation (Y). The R² value is 0.682, meaning that the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is 68.2%. While the remaining 31.8%, other variables amounting to 31.8 percent could be from medical treatment, costs, and travel services, which were not examined in this research.

INTRODUCTION

Kuala Lumpur is not the only favorite destination for Indonesian tourists in Malaysia. There is also Melaka, a country (province) in the Malacca Strait that has been designated by UNESCO as a World Heritage Site. Last year, as many as 678,572 Indonesian tourists visited Melaka. This figure shows an increase of 14.75 percent from the previous year, with a total of 591,324 tourists.

"Malays will not disappear from the world." The oath of Admiral Hang Tuah in the 15th century seemed to have received his "luck". When UNESCO designated Bandaraya Melaka as a World Heritage City on July 7, 2008, Since the beginning of the 15th century, the influence of the Malay Kingdom has been strong, followed by the entry of the Portuguese and Dutch in the 16th century, and the British in the 18th century replaced the Dutch position in Melaka after bartering with Batavia.

The influence of Indian, Chinese, and Arab cultures brought by traders is also clearly depicted in every museum diorama that is scattered throughout this city. Old European-style buildings fill every corner of Melaka City, Malaysia. When night falls, this old city looks even more exotic. Visiting the Melacca River Cruise or Jonker Street is the right choice. Since ancient times, Melaka has been famous as a trade center in Malaysia. A mixture of various cultures from all over the world is now leaving behind beautiful old buildings that fill the corners of this small town. Transportation to Malaysia is increasingly easy and affordable.

Malacca was recognized by UNESCO as a World Heritage City in 2008. This title is quite worthy of this old city. Their ability to maintain and preserve these old and historic buildings deserves a thumbs up. In fact, this area is now known as a tourist destination that can attract tourists from abroad. Red European-style

buildings are the hallmark of this city. The Melaka Church, Clock Tower, and Victoria Fountain are busy points for residents and tourists to experience the glory of Malacca's past. Around the old city area, you will definitely find lots of museums in every corner of the city.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Tourist Motivation

Motivation is a very basic thing in the study of tourists and tourism because motivation is a trigger for the travel process, although this motivation is often not realized by the tourists themselves. The study of tourist motivation has shifted from viewing motivation as a short process for looking at tourist travel behavior to placing more emphasis on how motivation influences a person's psychological needs and long-term plans.

Basically, someone who travels is motivated by several things. From various motivations that encourage travel, Motivations can be grouped into four large groups as follows:

1. Physiological motivation (physical or physiological motivation), including for relaxation, health, and comfort Participate in sports activities, relax, and so on.
2. Cultural motivation (cultural motivation), namely the desire to know the culture, customs, traditions, and arts of other regions. This also includes interest in various cultural heritage objects (historical monuments).
3. Social motivation or interpersonal motivation (social motivation), such as visiting friends and family, meeting work partners, doing things that are considered to bring prestige (prestige value), going on pilgrimages, or escaping from boring situations.
4. Fantasy motivation (motivation due to fantasy), namely the fantasy that in another area someone will be able to escape from the boring daily routine.

Tourism has six characteristics, including:

1. Service Industry Companies that form the tourism industry are service industry companies, each of which works together to produce products (goods and services) that tourists need during their stay. tourist trips to tourist destination areas.
2. Labor-Intensive What is meant by labor-intensive tourism as an industry is that it absorbs a lot of labor. A study says several percent of tourist spending in an area is used to pay wages and salaries.
3. Capital Intensive: The tourism industry is capital intensive, meaning that to build facilities and infrastructure for the industry, large amounts of capital are required for investment, but on the other hand, the return on invested capital takes a relatively long time compared to other manufacturing industries.
4. Sensitive The tourism industry is very sensitive to security and comfort. When going on a tourist trip, no tourist is willing to take risks on a trip done routine.

Based on the nature of the trip and the location where it is made, tourists can be classified as follows :

1. Foreign tourism, or foreign tourists, are people who travel on tour and enter a country other than the country where they usually live. The term foreign tourists is currently y popular
2. Domestic foreign tourist is a foreigner who lives or resides in a country and travels on tour in the territory of the country where he lives. This person is not a citizen of the country where he is located but is a foreign citizen (WNA) who, because of his duties and position, has settled and resides in a country.
3. Domestic tourist is a domestic tourist (WDN), namely a citizen who travels to his country; this kind of tourist is better known as an archipelago tourist.
4. Indigenous foreign tourists are citizens of a particular country who, due to their duties or position, are abroad and return to their country of origin to undertake tourist trips within the territory of their own country.
5. Transit tourist is a tourist who is on a tourist trip to a certain country by boarding an airship, ship, or train and is forced to stop at a port, airport, or station not of his own free will. Usually this happens when there is a change in the transportation used to continue the journey to the destination country, add passengers, or fill up with fuel and then continue the journey to the original destination. This long enough time for the changeover is used by passengers to tour the place they are stopping at.

6. Business tourist is a person who travels for purposes other than tourism, but the tourist trip is carried out after the main purpose has been completed. So a tourist trip is a secondary trip after the primary destination.

Table 1. Previous Research

No	Author Name	Heading	Result
1.	Hardianti, Syahdanur Kamar Zaman	Analysis of Tourist Decisions in Visiting National Parks Tesso Nilo Pelalawan	The research results show that factors social, personal, and psychological have a significant influence on tourists decisions when visiting Tesso Nilo National Park, and the psychological factor is the most dominant, with a calculated t value of 3,801. The coefficient of determination (R2) value shows that the independent variables studied were able to explain 74.1% of tourist decision variables, while the remaining 25.9% were explained by other independent variables not included in this study.
2.	Eko Haryanto 2019	Analysis Of Motivation Driving Foreign Tourists Visit Yogyakarta	They were dominated by 18- to 30-year-olds who traveled as a couple with friends and family members. Push motivation in the dimension of seeking relaxation is the most significant influence on foreign tourist decisions, followed by gaining knowledge, sightseeing variety, enhancing relationships, escaping the daily routine, and enhancing social circles. In fact, fulfilling spiritual needs and fulfilling prestige don't significantly influence tourist decisions to visit Yogyakarta.
3	Emi Hayati, Syofia Achnes, Andi M Rifiyan , 2018	Tourist Motivation Factors Visit Muara Takus Temple Kec. Xiii Koto Kampar Kampar District	This research identified four problems: physiological motivation, cultural motivation, social motivation, or interpersonal motivation, and fantasy motivation. Thus, in this research, the author can know

			what motivates tourists to visit Attraction Candi Muara Takus Kec. XIII Koto Kampar Regency Kampar.
4	Riki Darmadi, Waryono, Hijriyantomi Suyuthie 2017	Visitors' Drive To Tourism Objects Air Manis Beach Padang City,	The results of this research show that the motivation of visitors to visit the object of Air Manis Beach tourism in Padang City as a whole is in the good category, with an average value of 67.74. Meanwhile, based on indicators, (1) factor Internal is in the good category with an average value of 34.07. (2) External factors are in the good category with an average value of 33.67.
	AA. Bagus Putu Widanta, AA. Ketut Ayuningsasi	Analysis of Factors Affecting Tourist Interest in Domestic Visits to Bali	Image, infrastructure marketing, attraction marketing, people marketing, have a positive and significant effect, except that price has a positive and insignificant effect on the interest of domestic tourist revisit to Bali. Identification of variables that influence the interest of domestic tourists to be a reference for decision making and policies for related parties to develop the direction of tourism policies on Bali in particularly and Indonesia in generally

Source : Previous Research, 2023

METHODS

The population in the realm of this research is a description of the general conditions consisting of the research objects that will be studied. The population in this study were tourists who visited the Kota Lama Bandaraya Melaka. The sample in this research was 50 tourists who visited the Old City area of Melaka. Thsample in this research was 50 tourists who visited the Old City area of Melaka.

Research Data Collection Techniques Researchers conducted direct interview techniques with tourists visiting the Old City Bandaraya Melaka. Researchers also collected data through questionnaires given to tourists.

The data analysis method in this research uses a quantitative approach. Quantitative research is a research method used to research certain populations or samples, collecting data based on research instruments, analysis, and statistics with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses.

Multiple linear regression analysis is an analytical tool used to measure the influence of two or more independent variables on the dependent variable. The formula for multiple linear regression is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_1 X_3 + b_1 X_3 + e$$

Information:

Y = motivation to visit;

a = constant;

b = regression coefficient;

X1 = psychological motivation;

X2 = cultural motivation;

X3 = social motivation;

X3 = fantasy motivation.

e = Error Rate (error)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Descriptive statistics

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Motivasi psikologis	37	19	30	23.38	3.235
Motivasi cultural	37	14	24	18.00	2.603
Motivasi sosial	37	12	20	16.54	2.329
Motivasi fantasi	37	12	27	19.51	3.626
Motivai wisatawan	37	18	25	21.00	2.333
Valid N (listwise)	37				

Source : Processed Data, 2023

Psychological motivation has a minimum value of 19 and a maximum value of 30 for tourists. The average value is 23.38, and the standard deviation value is 3.235. Cultural motivation has a minimum value of 14 and a maximum value of 24 for tourists. The average value is 18.00, and the standard deviation value is 2.603. Social motivation has a minimum value of 12 and a maximum value of 20 for tourists. The average value is 16.54, and the standard deviation value is 2.329. Fantasy motivation has a minimum value of 12 and a maximum value of 27 for tourists. The average value is 19.51, and the standard deviation value is 3.626. e. Tourist motivation has a minimum value of 18 and a maximum value of 25 tourists. The average value is 21.00, and the standard deviation value is 2.333.

2. Validity Test

The significance test is carried out by comparing the calculated r value with the r table for degree of freedom (df) = n – 2 with alpha 0.05; in this case, n is the number of samples. In this study, df = 37-2 = 35, so we get the r table for df (35) = 0.324.

3. Reliability Test

The reliability test is used to measure a questionnaire which is an indicator of the variable. The questionnaire is said to be reliable if the answers to the statements are constant or stable over time. The data reliability test is used with the Cronbach Alpha method where an instrument is said to be reliable if it has a reliability coefficient greater than 0.60 (Ghozali, 2018).

Table 3. Reliability Test

Variabel	Standar	Cronbach's Alpha	Keterangan
Motivasi wisatawan(Y)	0,60	0,767	Reliabel
Motivasi psikologis (X ₁)	0,60	0,653	Reliabel
Smotivasicultural (X ₂)	0,60	0,853	Reliabel
Motivasi sosial(X ₃)	0,60	0,752	Reliabel
Motivasi fantasi(X ₄)	0,60	0,821	Reliabel

Source : Processed Data, 2023

It can be seen that the reliability coefficient of the independent and dependent variables shows that the Cronbach Alpha coefficient is > 0.60, so it can be concluded that all instruments in this research are reliable.

4. Hypothesis Test**a) Determination Coefficient Test:****Table 4. Determination Coefficient Test
Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.826 ^a	.682	.642	1.935

A. Predictors: (Constant), Motivasi Psikologi,, Motivasi Cultural, Motivasi Sosial, Motivasi Fantasi

B. Dependent Variable: Motivasi Wisatawan

Source : Processed Data, 2023

It is known that the R² value is 0.682, meaning that the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is 68.2%. Meanwhile, the remaining 31.8% is influenced by other variables not included in this regression model.

b) F Test**Table 5. F Test
ANOVA**

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	256.855	4	64.214	17.145	.000 ^b
1 Residual	119.848	32	3.745		
Total	376.703	36			

a. Dependent Variable: Motivasi Wisatawan

Source : Processed Data, 2023

It is known that F count 17.145 > Ftable 3.29 with Sig. 0.000 < 0.05. What this means is that the independent variables together have an effect on the independent variable.

c) T Test

Table 6. T Test Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	2.429	4.876		.498	.622		
1 MOTIVASI PSIKOLOGI	-.192	.129	-.155	-1.495	.145	.928	1.077
MOTIVASI CULTURAL	.038	.143	.028	.269	.790	.943	1.060
MOTIVASI SOSIAL	.484	.094	.543	5.145	.000	.894	1.119
MOTIVASI FANTASI	.682	.142	.492	4.808	.000	.949	1.054

a. Dependent Variable: Motivasi Wisatawan

Source : Processed Data, 2023

Hypothesis Testing Results H1 To see the effect of (X1) on (Y), the t statistical test is used. The t statistical test aims to partially test the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable by comparing tcount with ttable and seeing the significant value. Where tcount > ttable and sig.t < 0.05, then Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted. And vice versa, if tcount < ttable and sig.t > 0.05, Ho is accepted and H1 is rejected. It can be seen and compared that tcount-1,495 < ttable 2,037 and sig. 0.145<0.05. This means that the variable (X1), psychological motivation, has no effect on tourist motivation (Y).

Hypothesis testing results H2 To see the effect of (X2) on (Y), the t statistical test is used. The t statistical test aims to partially test the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable by comparing tcount with ttable and seeing the significant value. Where tcount > ttable and sig.t < 0.05, then Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted. And vice versa, if tcount < ttable and sig.t > 0.05, Ho is accepted and H1 is rejected. In table 4.1.6.1 below, the results of H2 testing are described. It can be seen and compared that tcount 0.269 < ttable 2.037 and sig. 0.790< 0.05. This means that the cultural motivation variable (X2) has no effect on tourist motivation (Y).

Hypothesis Testing Results H3 To see the effect of (X3) on (Y), the t statistical test is used. The t statistical test aims to partially test the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable by comparing tcount with ttable and seeing the significant value. Where tcount > ttable and sig.t < 0.05, then Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted. And vice versa, if tcount < ttable and sig.t > 0.05, Ho is accepted and H1 is rejected. It can be seen and compared that tcount 5.145 > ttable 2.037 and sig. 0.000<0.05. This means that the social motivation variable (X3) has an influence on tourist motivation (Y).

Hypothesis testing results H4 To see the effect of (X4) on (Y), the t statistical test is used. The t statistical test aims to partially test the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable by comparing tcount with ttable and seeing the significant value. Where tcount > ttable and sig.t < 0.05, then Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted. And vice versa, if tcount < ttable and sig.t > 0.05, Ho is accepted and H1 is rejected. It can be seen and compared that tcount 4,808 > ttable 2,037 and sig. 0.000<0.05. This means that the fantasy motivation variable (X4) influences tourist motivation (Y).

CONCLUSION

1. THE INFLUENCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL MOTIVATION ON TOURIST MOTIVATION The table above shows that tcount -1.495 < ttable 2.037 and sig. 0.145 < 0.05. With a significance level of 0.145, then h1 is rejected, which means that psychological motivation does not have a significant effect, meaning that the psychology or psychological motivation of tourists does not influence their motivation to visit the old city or red city of Melaka.
2. THE INFLUENCE OF CULTURAL MOTIVATION ON TOURIST MOTIVATION The table above can be seen and compared to show that tcount is 0.269 < ttable 2.037 and sig. 0.790< 0.05. With a significance level of 0.790, h2 is rejected. Showing that cultural motivation has no influence on tourist motivation, this explains why tourists do not take into account artistic and cultural customs when visiting the old city of Melaka

3. THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MOTIVATION ON TOURIST MOTIVATION The table above can be seen and compared, showing that $t_{count} 5.145 > t_{table} 2.037$ and $sig. 0.000 < 0.05$. With a significance level of 0.000, h_3 is accepted. Which partially means that social motivation has a significant influence on tourist motivation, meaning that social value or appreciation, recognition, and pride in the visiting experience are the main goals of tourists visiting the old city of Melaka.
4. THE INFLUENCE OF FANTASY MOTIVATION ON TOURIST MOTIVATION The table above can be seen and compared, showing that $t_{count} 4.808 > t_{table} 2.037$ and $sig. 0.000 < 0.05$. With a significance level of 0.000, h_4 is accepted. This means that the fantasy motivation variable partially influences tourist motivation, meaning that the aim of tourists visiting the old city of Malacca is to reduce boredom in dealing with daily routines.

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